

Monte Carlo Simulation of Phase Transitions in Heavy-Ion Collisions

L. F. Babichev and Y. A. Rusak

*Joint Institute for Power and Nuclear Research – Sosny,
National Academy of Sciences of Belarus, 99 Acad. Krasina Str, 220109 Minsk, BELARUS*
(Received 1 June, 2023)

In the present paper authors use UrQMD and modified HIJING Monte Carlo generators to describe STAR experiments results for fluctuations. Analysis shows that electric charge 3rd to 2nd cumulant relation can provide information about type of matter produced in heavy-ion collisions. Both generators describe experimental data decently (except for transport UrQMD part). Also, charged hadron distributions over different kinematic observables is presented for different equations of state in UrQMD Monte Carlo generator.

PACS numbers: 12.38.Mh, 25.75.Nq, 25.75.-q, 25.75.Cj, 24.10.Lx, 24.60.Ky

Keywords: quark-gluon plasma, fluctuations, heavy-ion collision, Monte Carlo simulation

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10034525>

1. Introduction

The search for arguments confirming or refuting the statement about the formation of a new state of hadronic matter – quark-gluon plasma (QGP) remains an extremely pressing issue in high-energy physics and relativistic nuclear physics. Its existence is justified by asymptotic freedom, a fundamental property of QCD. However, since calculating the properties of QCD matter from first principles of theory for finite baryon densities and low momentum region is a difficult task, finding the phase transition and determining its order occurs through experiment. Also, one needs to find experimentally observed quantities that behave differently under different states of the resulting medium. In 2005, four international collaborations published their measurements and announced the discovery of QGP (e.g., [1]). However, at the moment, some questions still remain open: the formation of strangeness, the order of the phase transition, the location of the critical point on the curve of the phase diagram, etc. Moreover, the behavior of some observable quantities can be explained without involving QGP or appear in pp or pA collisions (question about the formation of QGP in which is still open) [2–5]. Thus,

to study the medium obtained in heavy-ion collisions, experiments are both being carried out at the moment (NA61, BES) and planned in the near future (NICA, FAIR). The last two are particularly interesting because they study the part of the phase diagram in which, according to theoretical expectations, there can be phase transitions of both the first and second order.

The main research tool is the analysis of heavy-ion collisions with a large multiplicity of secondary particles. When analyzing such events, it is necessary to process huge amounts of experimental data and compare it with simulation results using various Monte Carlo (MC) generators. Such research can only be carried out with the help of modern supercomputer technologies, especially when it comes to the use of hydrodynamics.

The difficulty of detecting QGP in heavy-ion collisions is due to the impossibility of its direct observation. To resolve the issue of the possible formation of a QGP, various indirect criteria are used. One of these criteria can be the growth of fluctuations in multiplicity, charge, and particle ratios near the phase transition (PT) point. The disadvantage of using Monte Carlo simulation is the increased requirement for computer resources. However, the use of supercomputer technologies

makes it possible to carry out such calculations in a very reasonable time. In this work, we will use the HIJING generator [6], modified using various models of parton energy loss in a hot and dense medium, the use of which is justified for a given energy range, although it cannot simulate the entire range of collective phenomena observed experimentally. Also, we shall analyze the UrQMD Monte Carlo generators models and particle distributions over different kinematic variables.

2. Heavy-ion collisions and phase diagram of quantum chromodynamics

Quantum chromodynamics (QCD) is a theory that describes one of the fundamental interactions - the strong one. According to it, hadrons consist of quarks (baryons consist of three quarks, and mesons consist of two: a quark and an antiquark). But unlike quantum electrodynamics (QED), in which the potential between charged particles decreases as the distance between them increases, QCD has one very important property - asymptotic freedom. This means that hot/dense matter must be loosely bound [7]. This property creates the prerequisites for the existence of a new form of nuclear matter - quark-gluon plasma. It should be noted that asymptotic freedom is an exclusively high-temperature feature ($T \geq 120 - 150$ MeV). At low temperatures, quarks are “closed” in hadrons due to the QCD property of vacuum - confinement [8], so in the experiment we can only observe hadronic matter, but not free quarks.

Figure 1 shows the QCD phase diagram. Each point in the diagram corresponds to a stable thermodynamic state. Thermodynamic parameters are temperature and baryo-chemical potential, which shows the density of the total baryon charge of the system. When compiling such diagrams, QCD is taken on a lattice, which operates only at zero baryo-chemical potential. From the phase diagram, it can be seen that at a low baryo-chemical potential ($\mu \approx 0$), a crossover

between the two phases is predicted. With a magnification of μ_S , the so-called “sign problem” appears, which makes it impossible to use QCD on lattices. However, this part of the phase diagram is very important: it contains the region of the first-order phase transition and critical points. Thus, to draw the phase diagram beyond $\mu \approx 0$, various approximation and extrapolation techniques are used. Consequently, the exact boundaries of the media in the phase diagram are unknown experimentally [9].

FIG. 1: The QCD phase diagram.

It is believed that QGP was observed in nature during the first 10^{-5} s after the Big Bang and in the cores of neutron stars at the time of their collapse. Under terrestrial conditions, such a state can be obtained using heavy-ion collisions, which are used to study the processes of QGP formation and study the QCD phase diagram [10], including when compared with the results of experiments on pp and pA collisions. In order to detect QGP, various experiments on heavy-ion collisions have been carried out at existing colliders (SPS, RHIC, LHC), and experiments will also be conducted at new colliders (NICA, FAIR). Theoretically, these collisions are simulated using MC generators that use various models to calculate the cross

sections of processes occurring during the collision of heavy ions (HIJING, UrQMD, HYDJET++, pyquen). These models should adequately reflect the hadrons – QGPs – that occur during the phase transition. By comparing the simulation results with the experiment, we can draw a conclusion about the adequacy of the applied theoretical models.

The evolution of heavy-ion collisions occurs as follows. Two nuclei in the center of mass system, which look like two Lorentz-compressed “pancakes” with the longitudinal size smaller than the transverse size by a Lorentz factor $\gamma \sim \sqrt{s_{NN}}/2m_p$ for high-energy collisions. Afterwards, at a moment of proper time equal to $\tau = \sqrt{t^2 - z^2} = 0$ fm/s, the two nuclei collide. Hard processes occur first, i.e., which are accompanied by the transfer of a large momentum Q , $Q \geq 10$ GeV/s. At this stage, hard particles are born (whose transverse momentum is of the order of Q). Then most of the particles begin to collide. They form a dense medium that is not in a thermodynamic equilibrium. After that, there are two scenarios for the further development of the collision: the formed partons interact or not (the interaction can be neglected). The second scenario involves the rapid separation of partons from each other and hadronization (it is believed that such a scenario is realized in hadron-hadron and hadron-ion collisions). The first scenario assumes thermalization and, as a consequence, the formation of quark-gluon plasma, which is in local equilibrium. After this, the partonic substance begins to expand, becoming less and less dense, cools to the phase transition temperature and hadronizes [9].

It should be noted that in experiments on heavy-ion collisions, two parameters can be controlled: the collision energy and the number of hadrons participating in the collision (for collisions with a fixed target - only the number of hadrons from the projectile). The currently used relationship between experimental parameters and hadronization parameters on the phase diagram is represented by parameterization from [11].

3. Monte Carlo generators

Before conducting an experiment to determine the media formed in heavy-ion collisions, it is necessary, using Monte Carlo simulation, to have an idea of what observable quantities can provide information about the presence and type of phase transitions. There are three types of models: transport models, which are phenomenological, but operate with partons; hydrodynamic, in which a phase transition can be realized directly using thermodynamic quantities, and hybrid. In transport models, the various types of matter produced in heavy-ion collisions are usually modeled phenomenologically using on/off parameters or their values. In this work, we will use Monte Carlo generators HIJING, where the parameter that affects the types of matter formed is the loss of energy by the parton when passing through the medium, and UrQMD, in which a phase transition is implemented by different equations of state (EoS): the bag model EoS is for 1st order PT, the chiral EoS is for 2nd order, the hadron gas EoS is for no phase transition. The authors of this work implemented the models of parton energy loss in HIJING for both finite and infinite media.

3.1. HIJING

HIJING is a PYTHIA-based Monte Carlo generator. It combines a QCD inspired model for jet production with the Lund model for jet fragmentation. The formulation of HIJING was guided by the Lund FRITIOF and Dual Parton model for soft $A + B$ reactions at intermediate energies ($\sqrt{s} < \sim 20$ GeV/nucleon) and the successful implementation of perturbative QCD (pQCD) processes in PYTHIA model for hadronic collisions. HIJING is designed mainly to explore the range of possible initial conditions that may occur in relativistic heavy-ion collisions. To study the nuclear effects, we also included a nuclear shadowing of parton structure functions and a schematic model of final state interaction

of high p_T jets in terms of an effective energy loss parameter, dE/dz . At pp and $p\bar{p}$ level, HIJING also made an important effort to address the interplay between the low p_T nonperturbative physics and the hard pQCD processes. This Monte Carlo model has been tested extensively against data on $p + p(\bar{p})$ over a wide energy range, $\sqrt{s} = 50 - 1800$ GeV and $p + A$, $A + A$ collisions at moderate energies $\sqrt{s} \leq 20$ GeV/nucleon. However, in this version of the HIJING program, the space-time evolution of the final state interaction among produced partons and hadrons was not considered. A modification

of this generator is shown below.

Heavy-ion collisions can produce hot dense matter (QGP) and a cold hadronic medium. The energy loss of a parton in a hot medium consists of the following two parts: energy loss due to radiation and energy loss due to collisions of the parton with particles of the medium:

$$\left. \frac{dE}{dz} \right|^{total} = \left. \frac{dE}{dz} \right|^{collissional} + \left. \frac{dE}{dz} \right|^{radiative}. \quad (3.1)$$

Energy losses through radiation are in a BDMPS approach as [12, 13]:

$$\left. \frac{dE}{dz} \right|^{radiative} = \begin{cases} \frac{\alpha_s C_R}{8} \frac{\mu^2}{\lambda_g} L \ln \frac{L}{\lambda_g} & (L < L_{CR}), \\ \frac{\alpha_s C_R}{8} \sqrt{\frac{E\mu^2}{\lambda_g}} \ln \frac{E}{\lambda_g \mu^2} & (L > L_{CR}). \end{cases} \quad (3.2)$$

In turn, a part of the losses due to collisions is [14]:

$$\left. \frac{dE}{dz} \right|^{collissional} = \begin{cases} C_R \pi \alpha_s^2 T^2 \left[\left(A_g + A_q \frac{n_f^{eff}}{6} \right) \ln \frac{ET}{m_D^2} + O(1) \right] & \text{for u,d,s,g partons,} \\ \frac{4\pi\alpha_s^2 T^2}{3} \left[\left(A_g + A_q \frac{n_f^{eff}}{6} \right) \ln \frac{ET}{m_D^2} + \frac{2}{9} \ln \frac{ET}{M^2} + c(n_f^{eff}) \right] & \text{for c,b,t partons} \end{cases} \quad (3.3)$$

where $\mu^2 = 4\pi\alpha_s T^2 (A_s + A_q N_f^{eff}/6)$ is the Debye screening length of the medium, $C_R = C_g = N_c^{eff}$ is the gluon color factor, $C_R = C_q = (N_c^{eff} - 1)^2/(2N_c^{eff})$ is the quark color factor, A_g and A_q are the quantities characterizing the chemical equilibrium of the system (we take 1 to mean the system is in equilibrium), $\lambda_g = 1/(4\pi\alpha_s T)$ is the gluon mean free path, and $L = 3r_0 A^{1/3}/4$, $r_0 = 1.112$ fm is the transverse length of the resulting medium. Also, the energy loss due to radiation is characterized by $L_{CR} = \sqrt{\frac{\lambda_g E}{\mu^2}}$, which is a quantity characterizing the finiteness/infinity of the medium for the flying parton. In turn, the

effective number of aromas, the effective number of colors and the strong interaction constant, which depend on temperature, are expressed as [15]:

$$N_f^{eff} = \left[1 - 2\pi^2 \frac{T^2/Q^2 - T^2/Q_0^2}{\ln\left(\frac{Q^2}{Q_0^2}\right)} \right] N_f,$$

$$N_c^{eff} = \left[1 + \frac{8\pi^2 T^2/Q^2 - T^2/Q_0^2}{11 \ln\left(\frac{Q^2}{Q_0^2}\right)} \right] N_c,$$

$$\alpha_s = \alpha_s(Q, T)$$

$$= \frac{\alpha_s(Q_0)}{1 + \frac{\alpha_s(Q_0)}{4\pi} \left[\frac{11}{3} N_c^{eff} - \frac{2}{3} N_f^{eff} \right] \ln \left(\frac{Q^2}{Q_0^2} \right)},$$

$$N_c = 3, \quad Q_0 = m_Z = 91 \text{ GeV}.$$

The dependence of the temperature of the medium on the collision energy was obtained by fitting data from hydrodynamic calculations for various experiments [16] and is expressed as $T_0 = 0.1238294 (\sqrt{s_{NN}})^{0.2224218}$ GeV with the temperature profile of the medium $T = T_0 \left[2 \left(1 - \frac{r^2}{L^2} \right) \right]^{1/4}$. For a cold medium, we use only the parton energy loss due to radiation, the expression for which and all parameters are presented, for example, in [17].

To simulate first-order phase transition we assume, that centrality, required for the 1st order phase transition is achieved, the phase equilibrium c.m.s. energy is $(\sqrt{s_{NN}})$ GeV and the probability of the transition (ω) versus $\sqrt{s_{NN}}$ has distribution:

$$\omega_i(x_i) = \frac{1}{2} \left[1 - \operatorname{erf} \left(\frac{x_i}{\sqrt{2\sigma^2}} \right) \right], \quad (3.4)$$

$$x_i = (\sqrt{s_{NN}})_i - (\sqrt{s_{NN}})_b$$

where $(\sqrt{s_{NN}})_i$ is the c.m.s. energy in the i -th event, N is the number of events, $(\sqrt{s_{NN}})_b$ is the binodal c.m.s. energy, and σ^2 characterizes intensity of the fluctuations, that arise in the system (density, temperature e.t.c), thus, changing its properties and, in fact, is the width of such fluctuations distribution (Figure 2).

3.2. UrQMD

UrQMD combines two approaches to describe the evolution of heavy-ion collisions: transport and hydrodynamics. The transport part is based on the PYTHIA Monte Carlo generator [18] and is designed to describe all stages of a collision based on an efficient solution of the Boltzmann equation:

FIG. 2. Probability distribution of 1st order phase transition in event-by-event collisions versus $\sqrt{s_{NN}}$.

$$p^\mu \cdot \partial_\mu f_i(x^\nu, p^\nu) = C, \quad (3.5)$$

which describes the complete evolution of the distribution function over time for each type of i -th particle and contains the collision integral on the right side of the equation.

However, to model phase transitions in nuclear matter (transition to quark-gluon plasma), transport theory alone will not be enough, since during the formation of such a medium as QGP it is necessary to take into account the effects associated with the finite size of the formed medium (for example, various kind of correlation). Therefore, for these purposes, relativistic hydrodynamics is introduced into the generator, which will be better suited for describing the characteristics of the formed system.

Relativistic hydrodynamics is based on the conservation of energy, momentum and the resulting baryon charge. For hydrodynamic evolution, local equilibrium and zero viscosity are assumed (i.e., the mean path length is zero). The conservation of the described quantities is determined by the equations [18]:

$$\partial_\mu T^{\mu\nu} = 0, \quad \partial_\mu N^\mu = 0, \quad (3.6)$$

where $T^{\mu\nu}$ is the energy-momentum tensor and N^μ is the baryon charge. Expressions for these

quantities:

$$\begin{aligned} T^{\mu\nu} &= (\varepsilon_{lrf} + P)u^\mu u^\nu - P g^{\mu\nu}, \\ N^\mu &= \rho_{lrf} u^\mu, \end{aligned} \quad (3.7)$$

are the energy density, pressure, and density of the resulting baryonic charge, respectively (lrf is the laboratory reference frame), $u^\mu = \gamma(1, \vec{V})$ is the four cell velocity, and $g^{\mu\nu}(+, -, -, -)$ is the metric tensor.

Thus, modeling occurs in the following stages:

1. Initial state:

- initialization of two cores;
- nonequilibrium hadron-string dynamics (Lund string model);
- also includes fluctuations of the initial stage;

2. (3+1)-dimensional hydrodynamics with equation of state:

- SHASTA algorithm [19] for ideal relativistic hydrodynamics;
- equation of state for finite baryo-chemical potentials;

3. Final stage:

- hypersurface with constant energy density;
- hadron rescattering and resonance decays within the transport part of UrQMD.

It should be noted that the beginning of hydrodynamic evolution is calculated according to the equation:

$$\begin{aligned} t_{start} &= \frac{2R}{\gamma v} \\ &= \frac{2R}{\sqrt{\gamma^2 - 1}} = 2R \sqrt{\frac{2m_N}{E_{lab}}}, \end{aligned} \quad (3.8)$$

where R is the radius of the nucleus, m_N is the mass of the nucleon (proton), E_{lab} is the collision

energy in the laboratory frame of reference. t_{start} is at least 1 fm/s.

UrQMD implements the following equations of state:

1. Hadron gas, which includes the same degrees of freedom as the transport component UrQMD (hadron masses – up to 2.2 GeV);

2. Chiral equation of state from the quark-meson model with a first-order phase transition and a critical point (second-order phase transition);

3. Equation of state of the bag model with a first-order phase transition between the QGP and the hadronic phase.

This Monte Carlo generator works well at both low and RHIC energies, so it can be used to study and predict phase transition signals and determine the type of phase transition for experimental setups.

4. Results

4.1. Fluctuations of conserved quantities

Fluctuations and correlations have long been considered sensitive observable quantities to the phase structure of the medium formed in heavy-ion collisions [20–22]. They have a specific physical interpretation for systems in equilibrium and can provide information about the system's effective degrees of freedom. For example, QCD lattice calculations have shown that at the critical temperature there is a sharp increase in fluctuations of conserved quantities (resulting from the baryon, electric, and strangeness charge) near the transition point.

The most effective way to study fluctuations of a system obtained in collisions is to measure the observable quantity under consideration event by event and study the fluctuations on the basis of an ensemble of events [23]. In systems with strong interactions, the resulting charges of the system are conserved. As described above, event-by-event fluctuations and correlations of conserved quantities are observable quantities

with the help of which the properties of QCD matter in collisions can be studied. Although these observables are hadronic, it is believed that they may reflect thermodynamic properties of the early stage of collisions.

A system in thermodynamic equilibrium can be characterized by its pressure (which has no dimension), which is the logarithm of the QCD distribution function [24]:

$$\frac{P}{T^4} = \frac{1}{VT^3} \ln [Z(V, T, \mu_B, \mu_Q, \mu_S,)], \quad (4.1)$$

where V and T are the volume and temperature of the system, respectively, μ_B, μ_Q, μ_S , are the chemical potentials of the corresponding charges (B is baryon charge, Q is electric charge, and S is strangeness). The equations of state will be different for thermodynamic systems having different degrees of freedom and interaction. The susceptibility of conserved charges is defined as the derivative of the dimensionless pressure with respect to reduced chemical potentials:

$$\chi_{ijk}^{BQS} = \frac{\partial^{(i+j+k)} [P/T^4]}{\partial \hat{\mu}_B \partial \hat{\mu}_Q \partial \hat{\mu}_S}, \quad (4.2)$$

where $\hat{\mu}_q = \mu_q/T$, $q = B, Q, S$. Also, the cumulants of the distributions of these conserved charges are related to the corresponding susceptibilities, as

$$\begin{aligned} C_{ijk}^{BQS} &= \frac{\partial^{(i+j+k)} \ln [Z(V, T, \mu_B, \mu_Q, \mu_S,)]}{\partial \hat{\mu}_B \partial \hat{\mu}_Q \partial \hat{\mu}_S} \\ &= VT^3 \chi_{ijk}^{BQS}(T, \mu_B, \mu_Q, \mu_S,), \end{aligned} \quad (4.3)$$

where C_{ijk}^{BQS} are both diagonal and non-diagonal cumulants of the distribution of conserved quantities ($i, j, k = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$). When processing data, ratios of cumulants are constructed, since the cumulants themselves depend on the volume of the system (and therefore on fluctuations in collision centrality, which are purely statistical and are of no interest), but their ratios do not. Using the cumulant ratios, it is possible to directly compare them with the

susceptibility ratios obtained theoretically. The cumulants themselves, symmetry and kurtosis coefficients have the following form:

$$\begin{aligned} M_q &= \langle N_q \rangle = VT^3 \chi_1^q, \\ C_2^q &= \langle (\delta N_q)^2 \rangle = VT^3 \chi_2^q, \\ C_3^q &= \langle (\delta N_q)^3 \rangle = VT^3 \chi_3^q, \\ C_4^q &= \langle (\delta N_q)^4 \rangle = -3(C_2^q)^2 = VT^3 \chi_4^q, \\ S_q &= \frac{C_3^q}{(C_2^q)^{3/2}}, \quad \kappa_q = \frac{C_4^q}{(C_2^q)^2}, \end{aligned} \quad (4.4)$$

where $q = B, Q, S$; N_q is the resulting number of particles carrying the corresponding charge; $\langle \dots \rangle$ denotes an averaging over events, S_q is an asymmetry coefficient, κ_q is a kurtosis coefficient.

Next, the cumulant relations (4.4) are constructed. In what follows, by fluctuations of conserved quantities we will understand precisely the relations:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{C_2^q}{C_1^q} &= \frac{\chi_2^q}{\chi_1^q}, \quad \frac{C_3^q}{C_2^q} = \frac{\chi_3^q}{\chi_2^q}, \\ \frac{C_4^q}{C_3^q} &= \frac{\chi_4^q}{\chi_3^q}, \quad \frac{C_4^q}{C_2^q} = \frac{\chi_4^q}{\chi_2^q}, \end{aligned} \quad (4.5)$$

In present paper, we simulated STAR experiment using both UrQMD and modified HIJING Monte Carlo generators. A kinematic region description of STAR experiment can be found, for example, in [25].

Here and in the next graphs of this section designations are following: “STAR” denotes results of the STAR experiment, “inf+finite” denotes results fully implemented by (3.2), $dE/dx = 2$ GeV/fm for HIJING with jet quenching parameter set to 2, “cold” denotes a cold matter energy loss model, the option “no quenching” is default for HIJING with the quenching option set to 0, the option “UrQMD(T)” is for the transport UrQMD only, the option “UrQMD(HG)” is for UrQMD with hadron gas EoS, the option “UrQMD(BM)” is for UrQMD with bag model EoS.

FIG. 3: Net-electric charge fluctuations.

FIG. 4: Net proton number fluctuations.

FIG. 5: Rapidity distributions of charged pions (right) and protons (left) obtained within the framework of various equations of state.

Figure 3 shows net electric charge fluctuations. It can be seen, that both C_2/C_1 and C_3/C_2 relations agree reasonably with

experimental data, but C_2/C_1 relations do not show any differences in behavior for different models (except for transport UrQMD). However,

C_3/C_2 relations show that at high energy (200 GeV/n) inf+finite model describes experimental data better. Moreover, one can see information about energy loss model at high energies (>100 GeV/n).

Figure 4 shows net baryon (proton) charge fluctuations. It can be seen that C_2/C_1 relations differences in models behavior increase with energy. Moreover C_3/C_2 cumulants relations agree well with experiment, but don't show differences for models.

4.2. UrQMD kinematic observables distributions

Simulations using UrQMD model were made at 200 GeV/n energy and no special kinematic cuts. Analysis of charged hadron rapidity distribution for modified HIJING Monte Carlo generator can be found in [26, 27].

Figure 5 shows the distributions of protons (left) and charged pions (right) by rapidity y without kinematic restrictions for various equations of state:

$$y = \frac{1}{2} \ln \left[\frac{E + p}{E - p} \right]. \quad (4.6)$$

The particle rapidity distributions differ qualitatively between the transport model and the equations of state, but the difference between the equations of state is only quantitative.

Figure 6 shows the distributions of protons (left) and charged hadrons (right) over the transverse momentum p_T :

$$p_T = \sqrt{p_x^2 + p_y^2}. \quad (4.7)$$

It is clear from the figures that the distribution of protons is best suited for determining the resulting medium, since there is both a pronounced quantitative difference and a qualitative one (the peaks of the distributions are in different regions of the transverse momenta of the particles).

Figure 7 shows the distributions of protons (left) and charged hadrons (right) along the

azimuthal angle:

$$\phi = \text{arctg} \frac{p_y}{p_x}. \quad (4.8)$$

It is clear from the figures that there is no qualitative difference in the distributions along the azimuthal angle. The quantitative difference between the distributions is present only for all charged hadrons. Therefore, the distribution of particles over the azimuthal angle can be used to differentiate the formed media in the case of additional modeling of all detector limitations.

Figure 8 shows the distribution of protons (left) and charged hadrons (right) over the transverse mass m_T :

$$m_T = \sqrt{E^2 - p_z^2}. \quad (4.9)$$

It is clear from the figures that the difference in distributions is only quantitative. Thus, as with azimuthal angles, detector constraints must be accurately simulated. It should be noted that the location of the distribution peak in the case of equations of state is shifted by relative to the transport UrQMD for charged hadrons.

5. Conclusion

So, HIJING Monte Carlo generator is modified with different energy loss models. A brief description of UrQMD Monte Carlo generator is given. Both C_2/C_1 and C_3/C_2 relations agree reasonably with STAR experimental data for net electric charge fluctuations, but C_2/C_3 relations do not show any differences in behavior for different models (except for transport UrQMD). However, C_3/C_2 relations show that at high energy (200 GeV/n) inf+finite model describes experimental data better. Moreover, one can see information about energy loss model at high energies (>100 GeV/n). C_2/C_1 relations differences in models behavior increase with energy for net baryon (proton) charge fluctuations. Moreover C_3/C_2 cumulants relations agree well with experiment, but do not show differences for models. For UrQMD Monte Carlo

FIG. 6: Distribution of protons (left) and charged hadrons (right) by transverse momentum.

FIG. 7: Distribution of protons (left) and charged hadrons (right) by azimuthal angle.

FIG. 8: Distribution of protons (left) and charged hadrons (right) over the transverse mass.

generator, the particle rapidity distributions differ qualitatively between the transport model and

the equations of state, but the difference between the equations of state is only quantitative.

The distribution of protons is best suited for determining the resulting medium, since there is both a pronounced quantitative difference and a qualitative one (the peaks of the distributions are in different regions of the transverse momenta of the particles). There is no qualitative difference in the distributions along the azimuthal angle. The quantitative difference between the distributions is present only for all charged hadrons. Therefore, the distribution of

particles over the azimuthal angle can be used to differentiate the formed media in the case of additional modeling of all detector limitations. The difference in distributions over transverse masses is only quantitative. As with azimuthal angles, detector constraints must be accurately simulated. It should be noted that the location of the distribution peak in the case of equations of state is shifted by relative to the transport UrQMD for charged hadrons.

References

- [1] J. Adams *et al.* (STAR Collaboration). Experimental and theoretical challenges in the search for the quark–gluon plasma: The STAR Collaboration’s critical assessment of the evidence from RHIC collisions. *Nucl. Phys. A.* **757**, 102-183 (2005).
- [2] C. Blume. Open questions in the understanding of strangeness production in HIC – experiment perspective. *EPJ Web Conf.* **171**, 03001 (2018).
- [3] P. Biswarup. Charmonium production in p–Pb collisions with ALICE at the LHC. In: *Proceedings of European Physical Society Conference on High Energy Physics (EPS-HEP 2017)*: Venice, Italy, July 5-12. P. 182 (2017).
- [4] E. Shuryak. Strongly coupled quark-gluon plasma in heavy-ion collisions. *Rev. Mod. Phys.* **89**, 035001 (2017).
- [5] P. Koch, B. Mueller, J. Rafelski. From strangeness enhancement to quark-gluon plasma discovery. *Int. J. Mod. Phys A.* **32**, 1730024 (2017).
- [6] V. N. Russkikh, Yu. B. Ivanov, E. G. Nikonov, W. Norenberg V. D. Toneev. Evolution of Baryon-Free Matter Produced in Relativistic Heavy-Ion Collisions. *Phys. Atom. Nucl.*, **64**, 199-208 (2004).
- [7] E.V. Shuryak. Theory of Hadronic Plasma. *Sov. Phys. JETP.* **47**, 212-219 (1978).
- [8] S.A. Bass, M. Gyulassy, H. Stoecker, W. Greiner. Signatures of Quark-Gluon-Plasma formation in high energy heavy-ion collisions: A critical review. *J. Phys. G: Nucl. Part. Phys.* **25**, R1–R57 (1999).
- [9] K. Fukushima, T. Hatsuda. The Phase Diagram of dense QCD. *Rept. Prog. Phys.* **74(1)**, 014001(1-28) (2010).
- [10] Hui Wang. *Study of Particle Ratio Fluctuations and Charge Balance Fluctuations at RHIC*. (Thesis: PhD Michigan State U., 2012, 151 p.) e-Print: 1304.2073 [nucl-ex].
- [11] J. Cleymans, H. Oeschler, K. Redlich, S. Wheaton. Comprasion of Chemical Freeze-out Criteria in heavy-ion collisions. *Phys. Rev. C.* **73**, 034905 (2006).
- [12] R. Baier, Yu.L. Dokshitzer, A.H. Mueller, S. Piegne, D. Schiff. Radiative energy loss of high energy quarks and gluons in a fnite volume quark-gluon plasma. *Nucl. Phys. B.* **483**, 291-320 (1997).
- [13] R. Baier, Y. Dokshitzer, S. Piegne, D. Schiff. Induced gluon radiation in QCD medium. *Phys. Lett. B.* **345**, 277-286 (1995).
- [14] S. Piegne. Collisional energy loss of a fast parton in QGP. *AIP Conf. Proc.* **1038**, 139-148 (2008).
- [15] F. Stefens. The temperature dependence of running coupling. *Brazilian Journal of Physics.* **36**, 582-585 (2006).
- [16] I. Vitev. Hard probes to diagnose the QGP at the LHC. *JPG*, **30**, S791 (2004).
- [17] A. Mueller. Energy loss and p_{\perp} -broadening of high energy partons in hot and cold QCD matter. *Nuclear Physics A.* **610**, 459-469 (1996).
- [18] The UrQMD user guide. *The UrQMD group*. (Frankfurt, 2014). 51 p.
- [19] J.P. Boris, D.L. Book. Flux-corrected transport. I. SHASTA, a fluid transport algorithm that works. *J. Comp. Phys.* **11(1)**, 38-69 (1973).
- [20] V. Koch, A. Majumder, J. Randrup. Baryon-

- Strangeness Correlations: A Diagnostic of Strongly Interacting Matter. Phys. Rev. Lett. **95(18)**, 182301 (2005).
- [21] S. Jeon, V. Koch. Event by event fluctuations. Part of Quark-gluon plasma. **3**, 430-490 (2003).
- [22] V. Koch. Hadronic fluctuations and correlations. (ArXiv:0810.2520 [nucl-th], 2008) 34 p.
- [23] X. Luo, N. Xu. Search for the QCD critical point with fluctuations of conserved quantities in relativistic heavy-ion collisions at RHIC: an overview. Nuclear Science and Techniques. **28**, 112 (2017).
- [24] H.-T. Ding, F. Karsch, S. Mukherjee. Thermodynamics of strong-interaction matter from lattice QCD. Cornel. Lib. ArXiv: 1504.05274 [hep-lat] (2015). 72 p.
- [25] T.K. Nayak. Probing the QCD phase structure using event-by-event fluctuations. Cornel. Lib. ArXiv:2008.04643v1 [nucl-ex] (2020).
- [26] L.F. Babichev, Y.A. Rusak. Analysis of Charged Hadron Yield Distribution in Au+Au Collisions Using Different Parton Energy Loss Models. Int. J. Nonlin, Phen. Compl. Syst. **25(3)**, 306-311 (2022).
- [27] L.F. Babichev, Yu.A. Rusak. Monte Carlo Simulation of Fluctuations in Heavy-Ion Collisions for QGP – Hadron First-Order Phase Transitions. Int. J. Nonlin, Phen. Compl. Syst. **21**, 172-177 (2018).